

MICROMECHANICAL DESIGN OF CERAMIC/METAL FUNCTIONALLY GRADIENT COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Based on the micromechanical calculation for the effective material properties and macro thermal stress analysis of ceramic/metal functionally gradient composite materials, three Eshelby-type micromechanical methods (the mean-field method, the self-consistent method and the generalized self-consistent method) and interposing method for experimental data are evaluated for material design application. It is proposed in the material design that the two-phase micromechanical methods are closed to the experimental data when the material has low porosity, the three-phase micromechanical methods are good when the porosity is large and the three-phase generalized self-consistent method is better suitable to the materials with network structures.

Keywords: micromechanical design, functionally gradient composite material, thermal stress

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic/metal functionally gradient materials (FGM) are a novel composites for the future use of aerospace and nuclear engineering(Holt⁽¹⁾). The microgeometry of FGM is characterized by the continuous geometric transition from a dispersive structure to a network structure and from the network structure to an alternative structure. The optimize and control of the microstructure of FGM have an important effect on the macro-properties of FGM.

To optimize and control the microstructure of FGM, it is necessary to chose an efficient method to estimate the macro-properties of the FGM interlayers with different microstructures and mixture ratios. The purpose of this paper is to obtain some suggestions on the selection by investigated the estimating methods .

The common used methods now days are the simple mixing rule, the interposing method and the two-phase mean-field method (the dilute approximation micromechanical method). In these methods, the interposing method is the direct one and has been used frequently. To use this method, it is required to prepare several groups of FGM samples with specific mixture ratio, for example, the volume fractions of ceramic phase are 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0 , and obtain the properties of these samples by experimental method. By assuming the mixing ratios of the interlayers using the formula $c = (\frac{x}{d})^p$, the properties are estimating by interposing the tested data, Where c is the compositional distribution (the volume fraction of the ceramic phase), d is the distance in the interlayer, x is the layer location coordinate measured from the metal side, and p is the distribution exponent (Zhang etal⁽²⁾).

In this paper, we try to apply the Eshelby-type micromechanical theories to FGM. The Eshelby-type theories, including the mean-field theory, the self-consistent theory and the generalized self-consistent theory, have been applied in the designing of various composites. In section 2, we apply these theories to two typical FGM systems, one is a MgO/Ni system which has a large porosity, the other is a TiC/Ni₃Al system which has a low porosity. In comparison the computing results from the micromechanical methods with the experimental data, it is suggested that the two-phase theories are closed to the experimental data when the material has low porosity and the three-phase theories are good when the porosity is large. On the other hand, the three-phase generalized self-consistent theory is better suitable to the materials with network structures.

To evaluate the effect of these micromechanical theories and the interposing method on the thermal responses of the materials, the thermal stresses by the two micromechanical methods (the three-phase mean-field method and generalized self-consistent method) and the interposing method are analysed. From the results, it is indicated that the difference of thermal stresses between the two kinds of micromechanical methods are small but the difference between the micromechanical methods and the interposing method is obvious. It is suggested that the thermal responses have a dependence onto the estimating method and the selection must be carefully and need more theoretical analysis and experimental investigation.

REVIEW OF MICROMECHANICAL THEORIES IN APPLICATION TO FGM

(1) Review of The Eshelby-type Micromechanical Theories

The Eshelby-type theories are founded by Eshelby (Eshelby⁽³⁾) and developed by Weng, Laws and Benveniste, et al.

The mean-field method (MFM) is a kind of dilute approximate theory and it is a basic one in Eshelby-type methods. It can deal with the materials with dispersive microstructure but can't work well when the microstructure of materials are more complex (Weng⁽⁴⁾).

The self-consistent method (SCM) is based on the Eshelby's equivalent principle and the self-consistent theory. This method can deal with more complex materials without a special microstructure and it does not matter if these materials have apparent difference of the volume fractions of phases (Laws⁽⁵⁾).

The generalized self-consistent method (GSCM) is a more developed version of the ordinary self-consistent method. In this method, the influences among the particulates of different phases are considered more exactly and it can deal with some problems that the mean-field method and the self-consistent method can not be solved (Benveniste⁽⁶⁾).

(2) Application to FGM.

In the previous work⁽⁷⁾, we apply these micromechanical theories to two typical FGM systems: TiC/Ni₃Al system and the MgO/Ni system. Some results are given in Fig. 1-4 and the basic material properties are in Ref. [7].

In Fig. 1 and 2, the effective Young's modulus predicted by two-phase and three-phase mean-field methods are presented together with the experimental data. From Fig. 1 and 2, it is suggested that the two-phase theories are exact enough when the material porosity is small but it can't suit the case of material with high porosity level. In the meantime, the three-phase theories can be suitable for all the two cases.

Fig. 3 and 4 give the effective Young's modulus predicted by the three-phase mean-field theory, self-consistent theory and generalized self-consistent theory. It is expressed that the difference between the three kinds of methods is small and the generalized self-consistent theory

seemed to be more exact.

The variation of the Young's modulus and the shear modulus along the thickness for $p=1.0$ computed by the micromechanical methods and the interposing method are shown in Fig. 5 and 6. From Fig. 5 and 6, it is indicated that the variation of the Young's modulus and shear modulus along the thickness estimated by these two sorts of methods had some differences although the difference of the values was not so large.

THERMAL STRESS ANALYSIS OF FGM

(1) Model for the Thermal Stress Analysis

In this section, the thermal stresses of disk-like FGM plates generated in the fabrication are calculated. The geometry of the plates are 6mm in thickness, 30mm in diameter, 12 layers for MgO/Ni FGM and 11 layers for TiC/Ni₃Al FGM. In MgO/Ni FGM sample, each layer has the same thickness and in TiC/Ni₃Al FGM sample, the thickness of pure TiC side is 1mm and the rest layers are 0.5mm in thickness. The calculation condition for the thermal load is the same as the fabrication one (the sample is sintered at 1300°C and cooled down to room temperature). The material properties of the interlayers are estimated by the micromechanical methods and the interposing method. The compositional distribution in the FGM interlayers is assumed to take the form of $c = (\frac{x}{d})^p$.

Due to the axisymmetric problem, the axisymmetric finite element formula is employed. The cylindrical coordinate is chosen to be used and the Z-axis is taken along the thickness of the plate.

(2) Results and Discussions

Fig. 7 gives the thermal stresses of the MgO/Ni system based on the three-phase generalized self-consistent method and the interposing method. From Fig. 7, it is shown that the stresses based on the interposing method are higher for most distribution exponents, for example, for $p = 1.0$, the maximum tension stress by interposing method is 34.9 MPa while the stress by generalized self-consistent method is 14.9 MPa. The minimum values of the maximum stresses for the generalized self-consistent method and the interposing method appears at different p -values.

Fig. 8 shows the thermal stresses of the TiC/Ni₃Al system based on the three-phase mean-field method, the three-phase generalized self-consistent method and the interposing method. From Fig. 8, the curves for the two kinds of micromechanical methods are nearly same but the curve for the interposing method has obvious difference. For $p = 1.0$, the maximum tension stress by micromechanical methods is 140.8 MPa while the value by interposing method is 457.6 MPa.

From the results of the thermal stress analysis, it is expressed that the maximum stresses by three-phase mean-field method and generalized self-consistent method are similar. The maximum stresses by interposing method, however, are higher for most distribution exponents. On the other hand, the variation of the maximum thermal stresses with respect to the distribution exponents are also quite different. It is suggested that the method which is used to estimate the material properties of the FGM interlayers in the FGM optimum design should be chosen carefully, and needed more theoretical analysis and experimental investigation.

CONCLUSIONS

From the results of the micromechanics and thermoelastics, it is suggested:

(1) For the FGM systems with low porosity, the computed results by the two-phase Eshelby-type methods are closed to the results from experiment.

(2) For the FGM systems with large porosity, the two-phase methods can't suitable. The computed results by the three-phase methods are approached to the results from the experiment.

(3) The variations of the properties along the thickness of the two kinds of FGM systems which is estimated by the micromechanical methods and the interposing method have some differences although the differences of the values is not so large.

(4) For the FGM systems with low porosity, the maximum thermal stresses by three-phase mean-field method and generalized self-consistent method are similar and the variations of the maximum stresses by these two methods with respect to the distribution exponents are nearly same.

(5) For the both FGM systems which have small or large porosity, the maximum stresses by interposing method are higher than the maximum stresses by the micromechanical methods for most distribution exponents and the variation of the maximum thermal stresses with respect to the compositional exponent are also quite different.

REFERENCES

- (1) J. B. Holt and Z. A. Munir, Proc. 2nd Int. Symp. on FGM (FGM'92), Nov. 1-4, 1992, San Francisco, California, to be published by American Ceramic Society, Inc. (1993)
- (2) L. M. Zhang, R. Z. Yuan, Q. J. Zhang and X. F. Tang, Design and Fabrication of A MgO/Ni Functionally Gradient Material, Journal of Materials Synthesis Processing, Vol. 1, No3, 1993
- (3) J. D. Eshelby, The Determination of the Elastic Field of an Ellipsoidal Inclusion, and Related Problem, Proc. Roy. Soc. London, A241, PP. 376-396, 1957
- (4) G. J. Weng, Some Elastic Properties of Reinforced Solids, with Special Reference to Isotropic Ones Containing Spherical Inclusions, Int. J. Engng. Sci., Vol. 22, PP. 845-856, 1984
- (5) N. Laws, On the Thermoelasticity of Composite Materials, J. Mech. Phys. Solids, Vol. 21, PP. 9-17, 1973
- (6) G. Siboni & Y. Benveniste, A Micromechanics Model for the Effective Thermomechanical Behaviour of Multiphase Composite Media, Mech. Mater., Vol. 11, PP. 107-122, 1991
- (7) P. C. Zhang, C. R. Jiang and Q. J. Zhang, Application of Three-Phase Micro-Mechanical Theories to Ceramic/Metal Functionally Gradient Materials, Proc. 2nd Int. Symp. on FGM (FGM'92), Nov 1-4, 1992, San Francisco, California, to be published by the American Ceramic Society, Inc. (1993)

Fig. 1 Effective Y-modulus of MgO/Ni FGM predicting by the mean-field method

Fig. 2 Effective Y-modulus of TiC/Ni₃Al FGM predicting by the mean-field method

Fig. 3 Effective Y-modulus of MgO/Ni FGM predicting by three-phase methods

Fig. 4 Effective Y-modulus of TiC/Ni₃Al FGM predicting by three-phase methods

Fig. 5 Variation of the Y-modulus and shear modulus for MgO/Ni FGM along the thickness computing by GSCM and interposing method

- Y-modulus by GSCM ■ Y-modulus by interposing
- shear modulus by GSCM □ shear modulus by interposing

Fig. 6 Variation of the Y-modulus and shear modulus for TiC/Ni₃Al FGM along the thickness computing by MFM, GSCM and interposing method

- Y-modulus by GSCM ○ shear modulus by GSCM
- Y-modulus by MFM □ shear modulus by MFM
- ▲ Y-modulus by interposing △ shear modulus by interposing

Fig. 7 Maximum thermal stresses of MgO/Ni FGM with respect to various distribution exponents

- tensile GSCM ○ compressive GSCM
- tensile interposing □ compressive interposing

Fig. 8 Maximum thermal stresses of TiC/Ni₃Al FGM with respect to various distribution exponents

- tensile GSCM ○ compressive GSCM
- tensile MFM □ compressive MFM
- ▲ tensile interposing △ compressive interposing